

Asphalt Innovation Symposium 2025

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University of Antwerp
| SuPAR | Sustainable Pavements
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Sessie 2B

In-situ lifetime extension treatment of porous asphalt: Mechanical and rheological evaluation

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TNO

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 - Rheological evaluation – Crossover modulus and frequency
- Conclusions and recommendations

Introduction (1)

- Porous asphalt (PA): Air voids content $\geq 20\%$
- $\geq 90\%$ of the Dutch motorways are laid with PA surface layer
- Stormwater infiltration, reduced hydroplaning risk, reduced traffic noise

- Open structure of PA: Increased influence of environmental factors
- Accelerated ageing of binder and erosion of bituminous mortar

- Main failure mechanism: Surface stone loss (Ravelling)
- Average service life of the right (slow) lane: ~ 8 - 12 years¹

Need for sustainable maintenance techniques to preserve the pavement's condition and extend its service life

Introduction (2)

- In-situ treatment of PA with lifetime-extension agent (LEA)

- Goals of LEAs:

- ✓ Restore the aged binder's properties
Enhance its flexibility and stress relaxation ability

- ✓ Complement and strengthen the eroded mortar
With the aid of a bitumen and/or polymer component

- ✓ Provide a protective seal
Protect the bituminous mortar, slowing down the effects of moisture and ageing

- Various commercially available LEAs aiming to fulfill one or more of the above goals, depending on their composition

Research questions of the study:

1. Are LEAs capable of reducing the ravelling sensitivity of PA, treated in the field?
2. What is the effect of the various LEAs on the rheological properties of the field-aged binder?

Methodology (1)

Materials

Motorway	LEA	Type top layer	Treatment No.	Date of treatment
I	A	Single-layer PA 16 mm (PA16)	1 st	Sep-2022
II	A	Single-layer PA 16 mm (PA16)	1 st	Jul-2023
III	A	2-layer PA 5 mm (2LPA5)	1 st	Oct-2023
IV	B	Single-layer PA 16 mm (PA16)	1 st	Jul-2023
V	C & D	2-layer PA 8 mm (2LPA8)	2 nd	Jul-2024

- LEAs A, C and D aim to restore the field-aged binder's properties and strengthen the (eroded) mortar
- LEA B aims to strengthen and seal the (eroded) mortar (no restoration of binder's properties)
- 1st application of LEAs C and D on motorway V took place in 2018
- Ø150 mm field-cores right before and after 2-4 months of the treatment with LEAs

10-15 mm slice
Avoid dilution of LEA in
the total volume of
bitumen

Extraction and recovery of the
(treated) binder according to
EN 12697-3

Methodology (2)

Methods

Ravelling resistance

Rotating surface abrasion test (RSAT)

↓
@ 5 °C

↓
Stone loss ($\geq 2,0$ mm) after 24 hours

Rheological evaluation

Dynamic shear rheometer (DSR)

↓
Mastercurves @ 5 °C

↓
Crossover modulus (G_c^*) and
crossover frequency (f_c).

Results and discussion (1)

RSAT stone loss @ 5°C and 24 hours

- Both LEAs A and B enhance stone loss resistance, leading to increased durability
- LEAs A and B lead to sections with similar average stone loss sensitivity after treatment (0,8, 0,6 and 0,7 gr) for PA16, despite different compositions and initial ravelling sensitivity

- Sections treated with LEAs in 2018 show reduced ravelling sensitivity (on average) compared to the reference sections. LEA D more effective than LEA C (note: high variability in the results)
- Results of the 2nd treatment in 2024 show that the required re-treatment frequency may be LEA-dependent

Results and discussion (2)

Crossover modulus and frequency @ 5°C

- LEAs A, C and D lead to the increase of the G_c^* and f_c . Restoration (to some extent) of the properties of the field-aged binder
- LEA B shows opposite trend. Attributed to the components of LEA B which aim to strengthen and seal the mastic

Conclusions and recommendations

- All studied **LEAs** have been found to **reduce** (on average) the **ravelling sensitivity** of porous asphalt mixtures, which is expected to lead to the **life-time extension** of the treated sections.
- There are indications that different **LEAs** can have **varying effects on preserving the long-term ravelling resistance** of porous asphalt. This suggests that **re-treatment requirements** (e.g., 2nd, 3rd treatment) **may be LEA-specific**, with some requiring more frequent re-application than others.
 - ✓ *It is recommended that these indications will be further investigated in similar future studies.*
- The **RSAT** can **capture (on average)** the **differences** in stone loss **between the treated and untreated sections**. However, **high variability** in the results may **hinder safe conclusions** and differentiation between different LEAs.
 - ✓ *It is recommended, that upon usage of this test method in similar future studies, to consider to increase the number of test-samples to achieve greater accuracy in the results.*
- Based on the rheological results, most of the **studied LEAs** appear to **restore** (to some extent) the **properties of the field-aged binder**. On the other hand, **one** of the studied **LEAs** leads to **further stiffening of the field-aged binder**, underlying its **different composition and working principal** (i.e., strengthening and sealing of the mastic).
 - ✓ *The DSR is recommended as a useful tool to distinguish between various LEAs with expected different working principals.*

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Thank you!